

TWINNING MATTERS

Keeping Excellence Across All Regions

Twinning is one of the EU's most cost-effective tools for closing the research and innovation gap between Widening and established systems.

IMPACT IN NUMBERS

38%+

SUCCESS RATE
IN FOLLOWING
PROJECTS

3500+

TRAINED STAFF

120+

RESEARCH
PROJECTS

310

NEW
INTERNATIONAL
PARTNERSHIPS

KEY POLICY RECOMMENDATION

- Reinstate annual Twinning calls (2027 onwards) to maintain continuity.
- Anchor Twinning as a permanent excellence instrument in FP10.
- Adopt KPI-driven monitoring (mobility, open science, gender equality).
- Link Twinning outcomes with Cohesion Funds and Pillar II calls.
- Invest in people – the EU's most strategic resource.

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